

A STUDY OF SELF-CONCEPTS INFLUENCING STUDENT'S MATHEMATICS GRADES IN UNITAR

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics is one of the required core subjects in primary and lower secondary school. This research aims to identify if students' self-concept has a correlation towards students' mathematics grades during high school. The researcher will be using a quantitative approach to investigate the factors influencing foundation students' grades during high school at UNITAR International University. In this study, data and information were collected by questionnaire. An organized survey plan was utilized to catch information important to the investigation's targets and research questions. A total of 90 questionnaires will be given out to foundation students at UNITAR International University. The survey findings indicated an overall positive correlation outlook on students' self-concept, teacher influence and classroom climate on the factors influencing students' mathematics grades during high school. The finding of the study shows that the p-value for significant (2-tailed) is 0.046, which is lesser than 0.05; therefore, H1 is accepted in this research. It states that there is a link between pupils' self-esteem and their math grades during high school with the r-value of 0.211, which is a positive and weak correlation. Students who got D during high school did way better in their foundation. The researcher believes this is related to higher student ratings of their mathematical skills, abilities, enjoyment and curiosity.

Keywords: student's self-concept, mathematics, university students, UNITAR, questionnaire, SPSS

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the required core subjects in primary and lower secondary school. Numerous students believe that mathematics is a challenging subject and worry that they could not achieve excellent marks in mathematics, which negatively influences their learning experiences. Sadly, this supposition keeps amid school years places barriers to their ongoing mathematic development (Elçi, 2017). According to a growing amount of data, pupils' negative sentiments toward basic mathematics emerge early in their lives (Lorey, 2017), (Gafoor, Kurukkan, 2015). Accordingly, a few students have negative experiences towards learning mathematics, and along these lines, they may lose their self-confidence in mathematics (Ling, 2016). In addition, these people may start to feel that they are not sufficiently competent to learn mathematics and may not regard mathematics as their area of interest. Many college students who exhibit bad grades or lack of interest in mathematics are presented with negative experiences in secondary school math classes (Ruff, Boes, 2014). According to (Lorey, 2017), students who had poor

experiences may not be able to master the application of mathematical principles, lowering their mathematical competence essential for success in the workplace.

The objective of this research is constructed to identify if students' self-concept correlates with students' mathematics grades during high school. "I did not do well in mathematics" is an example of an item on the instrument (Tapia & Marsh, 2004). Students' views and attitudes regarding mathematics learning have traditionally been impacted by various factors, including individual students' knowledge and experiences and those of their lecturers and classmates. This indicates that a student's attitude toward learning mathematics might significantly influence their enthusiasm for the subject (Kele, 2014). While thinking about how students' emotional reactions affect their eagerness to participate in learning mathematics, the thought of personality turns out to be especially critical because it gives approaches to comprehending the multifaceted nature of students' decision-making (Andersson, Valero, Meaney, 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to (Gafoor and Kurukkan, 2015), students' perceptions of mathematics as difficult effect are not just their enjoyment of the subject but also their perseverance, benefit, boredom, and self-efficacy beliefs about mathematics. Self-efficacy does not refer to one's ability but rather to one's belief in one's own abilities (Gafoor, Kurukkan, 2015). According to (Ruff and Boes, 2014), the students come up short on the capability to understand the "why" of mathematics and rather displace state of mind. Math anxiety can be identified because of their dislike in mathematics. According to (Sandt and Brien, 2017), mathematics anxiety is an excessive sensation of concern about one's capacity to grasp and do arithmetic, a certain event, such as a math test, or certain conditions requiring math. Students' past negative or humiliating encounters with math made them dislike mathematics. Students may believe that they are bad at math because of their experiences.

Self-concept has been shown to be an important educational achievement (Lorey, 2017). (Oyedeji, 2017) indicator and a desirable mediating variable led to other positive outcomes to the point where self-concept enhancement is listed as a central goal of education in educational policy statements all over the world (Andersson, Valero, Meaney, 2015). Therefore, if students' self-concept is low, it will impact students' learning process.

The learning environment heavily influences the quality of academic accomplishment in mathematics. Researchers found that if a student's surrounding is physically, cognitively, or emotionally hazardous, it will be difficult for him or her to focus solely on learning (Shamaki, Ado, 2015), (Oyedeji, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The researcher will be using a quantitative approach to investigate the factors influencing foundation students' grades during high school at UNITAR International University. Therefore, the researcher will be using students' mathematics grades during high school (SPM) to indicate better students' self-concept in mathematics, teacher influence, and classroom climate.

The research will be conducted at UNITAR International University, Kelana Jaya, Selangor. This group of students will be easily accessible to the researcher and have a large number of students

to get the views on the perspectives of foundation students towards mathematics. The samples in the study are the foundation students in UNITAR International University, Kelana Jaya, which consists of a total of 90 foundation students who are currently in their first semester. Foundation students were chosen for the study for various reasons, one of which is that they are at the beginning of their academic careers.

In this study, data was collected by using a questionnaire. An organized survey plan was utilized to catch information important to the investigation's targets and research questions. A total of 90 questionnaires will be given out to foundation students at UNITAR International University. The researcher will personally go to the college to distribute and collect the questionnaires from the students on the same day.

Data collection for the questionnaire will be done using the common statistical software SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science).

Reliability test

The internal consistency of the two portions of the questionnaire and the reliability coefficients of all the variables were determined using the Cronbach Alpha Formula in SPSS. The Cronbach's alpha test will determine whether the test measures the variable appropriately. In general, values more than 0.6 are acceptable, and values more than 0.5 are unacceptable by using Reliability Instrument in SPSS (refer to table 1)

Table 1 : Rule of Reliability (Stephanie, 2014)

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Pearson Correlation and Linear Regression Analysis

The Pearson correlation coefficient, r , can be used to compare attributes ranging from -1 to 1. The stronger the linear link between the two variables, the further r is from zero. If the positive correlation is more than 0.9, it is considered strong and excellent to accept. The bearing of the relationship corresponds to the sign of r . If r is positive, the alternative tends to increase when one variable increases. If r is negative, then as one variable expands, the alternate will decline in general. A perfect direct relationship ($r = -1$ or $r = 1$) means that one of the elements can be brilliantly elucidated by the other's straight capacity.

RESULTS

Self-concept

Table 2: Self-concept descriptive

		B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10
N	Valid	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.28	2.46	2.80	2.48	2.47	2.50	2.54	2.61	2.70	2.18
Median		3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00
Mode		4	2	3	2	1	3	3	3	3	2
Std. Deviation		1.017	1.163	1.104	1.134	1.376	1.173	1.172	1.233	1.293	1.077
Variance		1.034	1.352	1.218	1.286	1.892	1.376	1.374	1.521	1.673	1.159
Skewness		-.389	.571	-.002	.434	.508	.555	.276	.234	.167	.796
Std. Error of Skewness		.254	.254	.254	.254	.254	.254	.254	.254	.254	.254
Range		4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Minimum		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Maximum		5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Percentiles	25	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.75	1.75	1.00
	50	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00
	75	4.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.00

Table 2 explains the students' self-concept in mathematics for this research and ten questions from B1 to B10 on students' self-concept towards students' mathematics grades. It shows the central tendency for each question, such as mean, median and mode, and dispersion, such as standard deviation, variance, range, lowest and maximum scores, percentile values, and skewness. The highest mean is 3.28 for question B1, and the lowest mean is 2.18 for question B10. The median is equally at 2 or 3. The highest mode is at 4, and the lowest is at 1.

The survey questionnaire had ten items on a five-point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4=Agree and 5- Strongly Agree). For this study, the response relating to students' self-concept toward their mathematics grades are listed below.

B1- Mathematics is easy for me.

Table 3: Frequency of item number 1 of student's self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	5.6	5.6	5.6
	Disagree	14	15.6	15.6	21.1
	Neutral	30	33.3	33.3	54.4
	Agree	33	36.7	36.7	91.1
	Strongly Agree	8	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1: Histogram of item number 1 of students' self-concept in mathematics

The table above on question B1 shows that most of the students answered agree with the frequency of 33 (36.7%) respondents, whereas 5 (5.6%) respondents answered strongly disagree with the lowest responsive value.

B2 - No matter how hard I try, I cannot understand mathematics

Table 4: Frequency of item number 2 of student's self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	21	23.3	23.3	23.3
	Disagree	28	31.1	31.1	54.4
	Neutral	27	30.0	30.0	84.4
	Agree	7	7.8	7.8	92.2
	Strongly Agree	7	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Histogram of item number 2 of students' self-concept in mathematics

The table above on question B2 shows the majority of the students answered disagree with the frequency of 28 (31.1%) respondents, whereas a total of 14 (15.6%) respondents answered agree and strongly agree, which has the lowest responsive value.

B3 - I often think, "I cannot do it," when a mathematics problem seems hard.

Table 5: Frequency of item number 3 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	14.4	14.4	14.4
	Disagree	21	23.3	23.3	37.8
	Neutral	32	35.6	35.6	73.3
	Agree	19	21.1	21.1	94.4
	Strongly Agree	5	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Histogram of item number 3 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B3, shows majority of the students answered neutral with the frequency of 32 (35.6%) respondents, whereas 5(5.6%) respondents answered strongly agree, which has the lowest responsive value.

B4 - I do not do well in mathematics

Table 6: Frequency of item number 4 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	20	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Disagree	28	31.1	31.1	53.3
	Neutral	26	28.9	28.9	82.2
	Agree	11	12.2	12.2	94.4
	Strongly Agree	5	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4: Histogram of item number 4 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B4, most of the students answered disagree with the frequency of 28 (31.1%) respondents, whereas 5(5.6%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B5 - When I hear the word mathematics, I have a feeling of dislike

Table 7: Frequency of item number 5 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	30	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Disagree	21	23.3	23.3	56.7
	Neutral	16	17.8	17.8	74.4
	Agree	13	14.4	14.4	88.9
	Strongly Agree	10	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5: Histogram of item number 5 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B5, shows majority of the students answered strongly disagree with the frequency of 30 (33.3%) respondents, whereas 10 (11.1%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B6 - Working numbers upset me

Table 8: Frequency of item number 6 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	20	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Disagree	27	30.0	30.0	52.2
	Neutral	29	32.2	32.2	84.4
	Agree	6	6.7	6.7	91.1
	Strongly Agree	8	8.9	8.9	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6: Histogram of item number 6 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B6, shows majority of the students answered neutral with the frequency of 29 (32.3%) respondents, whereas 6 (6.7%) respondents answered agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B7 - It makes me nervous to even think about doing mathematics

Table 9: Frequency of item number 7 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	21	23.3	23.3	23.3
	Disagree	23	25.6	25.6	48.9
	Neutral	27	30.0	30.0	78.9
	Agree	14	15.6	15.6	94.4
	Strongly Agree	5	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 7: Histogram of item number 7 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B7, shows majority of the students answered neutral with the frequency of 27 (30%) respondents, whereas 5 (5.6%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B8 - It scares me to have to take mathematics

Table 10: Frequency of item number 8 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	22	24.4	24.4	24.4
	Disagree	19	21.1	21.1	45.6
	Neutral	28	31.1	31.1	76.7
	Agree	14	15.6	15.6	92.2
	Strongly Agree	7	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 8: Histogram of item number 8 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B8, shows majority of the students answered neutral with the frequency of 28 (31.1%) respondents, whereas 7 (7.8%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B9 - The only reason I am taking mathematics is because I must

Table 11: Frequency of item number 9 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	22	24.4	24.4	24.4
	Disagree	17	18.9	18.9	43.3
	Neutral	26	28.9	28.9	72.2
	Agree	16	17.8	17.8	90.0
	Strongly Agree	9	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 9: Histogram of item number 9 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B9, shows majority of the students answered neutral with the frequency of 26 (28.9%) respondents, whereas 9 (10%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

B10 - I do not understand why I must learn mathematics

Table 12: Frequency of item number 10 of students' self-concept in mathematics

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	28	31.1	31.1	31.1
	Disagree	31	34.3	34.4	65.6
	Neutral	22	24.4	24.4	90.0
	Agree	5	5.6	5.6	95.6
	Strongly Agree	4	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 10: Histogram of item number 10 of students' self-concept in mathematics

According to the table above on question B10, shows majority of the students answered disagree with the frequency of 31 (34.4%) respondents whereas 4 (4.4%) respondents answered strongly agree that has the lowest responsive value.

Reliability

Table 13: Cronbach's Alpha for all the variables

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
0.770	30

Table 13 explains the reliability for all the variables, which is at 0.770. According to Table 1, 0.7 means acceptable; therefore, all the three variables are acceptable reliability in the research.

Pearson Correlation

the research question involves in this research is: What is the correlation between students' self-concept towards students' mathematics grades during high school?

H0: There is no correlation between students' self-concept towards mathematics grades during high school.

H1: There is a correlation between students' self-concept towards mathematics grades during high school.

Table 14: Correlation of students' self-concept and students' SPM grades

		Self-concept	SPM
Self-concept	Pearson Correlation	1	.211*
	Sig. (2- tailed)		.046
	N	90	90
SPM	Pearson Correlation	1	.211*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.046	
	N	90	90

*Correlation is significant at the level 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Discussion: The result from table 14 shows that the p-value for significant (2-tailed) is 0.046, which is lesser than 0.05. Hence, we need to reject the H₀. Accepting H₁ defines there is a correlation between students' self-concept and students' mathematics grades during high school with the r-value of 0.211, which is a positive but weak correlation.

Conclusion: Therefore, reject H₀, accept H₁

CONCLUSION

The study illustrates that students have well-articulated views regarding their learning and school experiences in learning mathematics. The complexity of the study and the topic became apparent throughout the research project. The survey findings indicated an overall positive correlation outlook on students' self-concept, teacher influence and classroom climate on the factors influencing students' mathematics grades during high school. In conclusion of this study, students' self-concept, teacher influence, and classroom climate have an impact on students' mathematics grades during high school.

Students' self-concept influence students' mathematics grades during high school. The finding of the study shows that the p-value for significant (2-tailed) is 0.046, which is lesser than 0.05; therefore, H₁ is accepted in this research. It states that there is a positive correlation between students' self-concept and their mathematics grades during high school, with a r-value of 0.211. Students who got D during their high school did way better in their foundation. The study is linked to students' improved judgements of their arithmetic skills, talents, enjoyment, and interest. Students' self-concept does not develop naturally; it is shaped by their social and physical contexts over time. According to (Gadoor and Kurukkan, 2015), many students have a high expectation of arithmetic difficulty but a low personal value associated with math.

Throughout elementary and secondary school, the school environment, social groups, and parents all have a significant role in forming self-concept and shallowness in children. The perception of trust in a person's capacity to do well in mathematics, or self-confidence in studying mathematics, is referred to as their mathematics self-concept (Andersson, Valero, Meaney, 2015). The way a person thinks, feels, behaves, values and judges oneself or herself in connection to mathematical performance is described as self-concept in this study.

As a result of this study's examination of students' views involving students' self-concept, teacher effect and lecture room, implications for administrators and instructors emerged. For administrators, this research published the essential want leaders to set up a fine lecture room climate for each instructor and college students (Andersson, Valero, Meaney, 2015), (Shamaki, Ado, 2015), (Oyedeki, 2017), based totally on student's assessment of the study room climate. For teachers, the research furnished a deeper perception of the perspective basis college students

related to what helps them examine better. Students who experienced negative conflict with their teacher were less successful academically.

This study took place in one participating university located in the Kelana Jaya, Selangor; therefore, results are only applicable to similar campuses and districts in terms of size and demographics. Data collection from larger populations and samples may produce different results. A recommendation for future research would be to include more middle schools or conduct the study at the elementary and high school levels to determine how the needs of students differ based on educational level. Future research could also focus its efforts on examining the ratio of the need for alternative methods, strategies, curricula, and professional development necessary to help meet the need of teaching students math. Finally, data should be collected on teacher education programs and professional development offerings provided to teachers related to classroom climate. This type of research could provide more insight into examining students' perceptions of teacher performance.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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